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Deliverable D6.4
Second report on training courses/workshops

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D6.4 Second report on training courses/workshops

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1 Executive Summary

MaX organized an impressive set of education and training activities. This deliverable is a detailed report, including links to the programs and data on users' participation and involvement.

In D6.1 we proposed our structured "Education and Training plan", aimed at bridging the skills gap between HPC development and computational materials science. In D6.3 we reported about the activities carried out in the first 18 months. Now we are reporting about the last 18 months (M19-M36). All the activities forecasted in the plan have been implemented.

The main actions include:

- a. 12 training initiatives --schools, tutorials, workshops-- directly designed, organized and co-funded by MaX (sometimes in cooperation with others). The emphasis was on hands-on-activities based on MaX flagship codes and frontier HPC developments, and on the involvement of young participants. The overall assessment of these initiatives by the participants (approx. 350 in total) was extremely positive.
- b. A few lectures/modules offered by MaX within schools organized by other institutions.
- c. Major contributions to innovative education pilots within three University MSci courses.
- d. 23 'training through research' visits in MaX laboratories.

These initiatives have resulted in the production of valuable training material handed out to students. Some of the training material prepared for these events is available to the broader community as it has been published in the training section of the MaX website.

Most partners have been heavily involved in the activities: Juelich, CNR, SISSA, ICN2, EPFL, CINECA, BSC, ETH Zürich, and UNESCO. Importantly, a significant number of activities have combined synergic contributions from different MaX partners with complementary expertise.

Finally, MaX is maintaining an online repository of training initiatives of interest to the computational materials research community, which is useful to potential participants and also helps organizers in coordinating, identifying needs and avoiding overlaps.

2 Repository of existing initiatives

MaX maintains a repository with information on training courses and workshop of relevance for its domain and community. This is available in the MaX website (see D6.2 for details) at the address <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/>. A list of events is given at the page <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/list-of-workshops-schools/> where events organized or supported directly by MaX are conveniently flagged.

More information on activities organized or supported by MaX are also displayed at the Events section of the website <http://www.max-centre.eu>.

3 Training events

3.1 Courses on individual codes/ HPC developments/on new methods-software

As defined in D6.1 chapter 3, MaX is engaged to organize specific training workshops and courses dedicated to scientists in the materials field, at different levels, with emphasis on hands-on courses. The aim is to give training by providing technical information and knowledge attracting especially young researchers. This task is coordinated by SISSA and CNR.

In the following a description of schools and training workshops organized by MaX from month 19. According to MaX strategy, we have chosen to organize directly a limited number of events of direct relevance for the CoE activities (other training actions are described in the following sections). Note that these events have often involved the contribution of more than one (sometimes several) partners of MaX.

List of schools:

- 1 MARVEL-MaX meeting and advanced AiiDA tutorial
- 2 Advanced computing of excited state properties in solids and nanostructures with Yambo
- 3 All electron DFT with FLEUR – a Hands-on Tutorial
- 4 SIESTA school on efficient DFT calculations using atomic orbitals
- 5 Second edition of the MARVEL/Psi-k/MaX AiiDA tutorial at EPFL
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1. MARVEL-MaX meeting and advanced AiiDA tutorial

Venue & date: EPFL, Lausanne (CH) - March 6-7, 2017

Organizers: MaX, Marvel.

Speakers: Nicolas Mounet, Martin Uhrin, Sebastiaan Huber, Rico Hauselmann, Giovanni Pizzi, Spyros Zoupanos.

Topics: This meeting with both MARVEL and MaX members aimed to encourage collaborations and to discuss about integration of workflows, plugins and curated data within AiiDA and Materials cloud. During the event, an advanced AiiDA tutorial for experienced AiiDA users has been held.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 20

Involvement: In the break out sessions, collaborators were grouped with core developers of AiiDA, such that they could describe in detail the road blocks they were encountering in using AiiDA, and what added functionality would help their particular use case. Collaborators reported interacting face-to-face with the core developers was really useful to solve ongoing problems and gain insight in the current development of AiiDA.

Website: <http://nccr-marvel.ch/de/events/marvel-max-meeting-march-2017>

The event has been recorded and videos uploaded to the Materials Cloud YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC-NZvRRQ5VzT2wKE5DM1N3A/featured>

2. Advanced computing of excited state properties in solids and nanostructures with Yambo

Venue & date: CECAM-HQ-EPFL, Lausanne (CH)– April 24-28, 2017

Organizers: MaX, CECAM, Psi-K, University of Luxembourg.

Speakers: Andrea Marini, Nicola Marzari, Davide Sangalli, Conor Hogan, Pedro Melo, Andrea Ferretti, Daniele Varsano, Carlo Cavazzoni, Myrta Gruning, Maurizia Palumbo, Xavier Blase, Henrique Pereira Coutada Miranda.

Topics: The school provided a balanced training both in the fundamental theory of electronic and optical excitations as well as strategies for practical computation within a massively parallel environment. The school combined invited keynote talks, lectures and hands-on sessions. Theoretical lessons: Many-body perturbation theory, one-particle excitations, the application of the GW approach and its implementation in Yambo, two-particle excitations in molecules and extended systems, the Bethe-Salpeter equation and its application to obtain the optical spectra with excitonic effects, realistic simulation of complex materials, trends in parallel computing, and the Bethe-Salpeter approach using a localized basis approach.

Practical tutorials: Yambo code, GW approach to obtain the quasi-particle energies and the performance of robust convergence tests, among other advanced topics, how to use Yambo to calculate optical spectra, the post-processing tools, and the exciton analysis. Use of the parallelism in Yambo and its efficient use in High-Performance Computing centers, Yambopy, a python interface that will allow you to automate calculations (such as convergence tests) with Yambo.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 44

Involvement: The course received very positive feedback from the participants. For details see attachment D6.4-A1

Website: <https://www.cecam.org/workshop-0-1386.html>

3. All electron DFT with FLEUR – a Hands-on Tutorial

Venue & date: Forschungszentrum Juelich (DE)- May 8-12, 2017

Organizers: MaX, CECAM

Speakers: Nicole Helbig, Daniel Wortmann, Gregor Michalicek, Stefan Blügel, Gustav Bihlmayer, Jan-Philipp Hanke, Davide Campi, Jens Bröder, Uliana Alekseeva, Christoph Friedrich, Irene Aguilera, Ersoy Şaşıoğlu, Mathias C.T.D. Müller, Bernd Zimmermann.

Topics: The tutorial focused on training the participants in using our all-electron FLAPW DFT code FLEUR and associated codes like Spex-FLEUR, a code for many-body perturbation theory, and G-FLEUR, an embedding code. In extension to similar previous tutorials it also addressed the usage of FLEUR within the AiiDA infrastructure to build automatic workflows applicable to materials screening applications. The tutorial covered theoretical lectures to provide the necessary methodological and physical background to professionally use the FLEUR code family and enable the participants to benefit from the strengths of the codes. Hands-on sessions were provided to get in touch with the codes from a practical perspective.

The school consisted of lectures covering three main areas:

1. the underlying basic theory,
2. the installation and usage of FLEUR and its AiiDA interface,
3. more specialized theoretical description relevant for typical FLEUR calculations.

In detail, the lectures were focused on:

- Introduction to density functional theory
- The linearized augmented plane-wave method
- Exchange-correlation functionals
- Magnetism and spin-orbit coupling

- Wannier functions
- The GW approximation and Green function embedding
- FLEUR features and requirements
- Parallel computing with FLEUR
- Aiiida for automatizing and documenting Fleur calculations

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 29

Website: <https://www.cecam.org/workshop-0-1421.html>

4. Siesta school on efficient DFT calculations using atomic orbitals

Venue & date: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona (ES) – May 23-26, 2017

Organizers: MaX, ICN2

Speakers: Alberto García, Roberto Robles, Ramón Cuadrado, Stephan Mohr, Marivi Fernández-Serra, Andrei Postnikov, Pablo Ordejón, Daniel Sánchez-Portal, Rafi Ullah, Javier Junquera.

Topics: This SIESTA school was a four-day hands-on tutorial on the use of the SIESTA code, aimed at students and researchers from different disciplines who already use, or plan to use, SIESTA in their work and who would like to understand its essential foundations and to learn how to apply the code effectively.

The course explained the theory behind electronic structure calculations and DFT, and showed standard tasks implemented in many DFT codes, but also covered topics which are more specific to SIESTA.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 20

Involvement: The course received very positive feedback from the participants. For details see attachment D6.4-A2

Website:

<https://www.bsc.es/education/training/other-training/siesta-school-the-european-centre-excellence-max>

5. Second edition of the MARVEL/Psi-k/MaX AiiDA tutorial

Venue & date: EPFL, Lausanne (CH) – May 29-31, 2017

Organizers: Max, MARVEL, Psi-K

Speakers: Invited: Dr. Thomas Bligaard (Stanford University, USA), Prof. Marco Fornari (Central Michigan University, USA), Prof. Chris J. Pickard (Univ. of Cambridge, UK), Prof. Stefano Sanvito (Trinity College Dublin, IRL). Lecturer: Fernando Gargiulo, Sebastiaan Huber, Leonid Kahle, Nicolas Mounet, Giovanni Pizzi, Martin Uhrun, Snehal Waychal, Spyros Zoupanos.

Topics: The tutorial was targeted at students, postdocs and researchers interested in applying high-throughput computations in their research, and in particular to those interested in learning how to use the AiiDA platform. The programme included a tutorial on the AiiDA code, and four invited highlight talks from experts in the field of high-throughput computations

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 37

Involvement: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive. 92.8% of the participants declared that they would strongly recommend their colleagues to participate to a similar tutorial on high-throughput computations using AiiDA. Also, 75% of the participants said they would like to participate in advanced AiiDA tutorials on topics like workflow development. For details see attachment D6.4-A3

Website: <http://nccr-marvel.ch/events/aiida-tutorial-may-2017>

6. Electronic Structure Library Coding Workshop: Drivers

Venue & date: ICTP, Trieste (IT) – July 9-22, 2017

Organizers: MaX, E-CAM, Psi-K, SISSA

Speakers: Volker Blum (ELSI), Viktor Yu (ELSI), William Huhn (ELSI), David Lopez (Siesta), Yann Pouillon (Abinit), Micael Oliveira (Octopus & Abinit), Fabiano Corsetti (Siesta & Onetep), Paolo Giannozzi (QE), Anoop Chandran (QE), Pietro Delugas (QE), Ivan Carnimeo (QE), Emine Kucukbenli (QE), Layla Martin-Samos (QE), Stefano de Gironcoli (QE), Ivan Girotto (QE).

Topics: The fourth edition of the ESL coding workshop focused on the theme of "drivers". In particular: drivers for KS and drivers for linearised KS.

During the two-week coding workshop the team of 15 coders, connected with several different electronic structure codes, gathered to build examples of stand-alone KS and/or linearised KS solution drivers, agnostic of the specific data structure of the codes that would use them.

Type of event: (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 15

Involvement: The workshop has received very positive feedback from the participants. The git repository of the software packaged during the workshop, hosted by the gitlab.e-cam2020.eu/ server in Lausanne, contains a copy of the KS_Solvers, FFTXlib, LAXlib and UtilXlib libraries of the Quantum ESPRESSO code, together with a toy code demonstrating their use to perform a simple but complete Cohen & Bergstresser empirical pseudopotential calculation. The repository and its content are publicly available and allow scientists and developers not familiar with the complexity of modern electronic structure codes to experiment and develop new methods for the diagonalization of large sparse matrices without being tied to a specific major code. The developed software can immediately be used by any code adopting the same API conventions.

Website: <http://indico.ictp.it/event/8050/>

7. Second AiiDA coding week

Venue & date: Leukerbad (CH) Oct. 16-20, 2017

Organizers: MaX, MARVEL

Speakers: not applicable.

Topics: This coding week was organized to improve the plugin system of AiiDA that allows one to extend it to be used with any HPC code.

In this case particularly, the core developers of AiiDA and all the MaX flagship codes, convened to discover the current limitations and bottlenecks in that process.

Great strides were made in writing the plugins for the MaX flagship codes, including the development of turnkey solution workflows using AiiDA's workflow engine.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 20

Website: <http://www.aiida.net/news/outcome-of-the-aiida-coding-week-video/>

Video summary from the participants is uploaded at: <https://youtu.be/GI4mIU7lmbw>

8. Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale

Venue & date: CINECA, Bologna (IT) – December 4-6, 2017

Organizers: MaX, CINECA

Speakers: Fabio Affinito, Davide Sangalli, Andrea Ferretti, Pietro Bonfa, Anton Kozhenikov, Anoop Kaithalikunnel, Antimo Marrazzo, Luigi Genovese.

Topics: The workshop focused on state of the art of the different HPC architecture and on the MaX flagship codes, Quantum ESPRESSO, Yambo, Fleur, Siesta, SIRIUS and the AiiDA framework. The exploitation of these codes, and their implemented algorithms, on the present and upcoming HPC architectures have been presented and discussed.

Type of event: (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes. Course on HPC development.

No. participants: 19

Involvement: The feedback received from the participants was satisfactory, even if not optimal. The average score was 7.08/10 from 12 filled questionnaires. The overall structure of the course, consisting in single seminars covering vertical aspects of the HPC codes in material science, received different feelings: some of the talks were very much appreciated and others were considered less attracting. In next editions, we will consider a change to address the comments of the students.

Website:

<https://eventi.cineca.it/en/hpc/material-science-codes-innovative-hpc-architectures-targeting-exascale>

9. PRACE-MaX Tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using AiiDA

Venue & date: CINECA, Bologna (IT) – May 30- June 1, 2018

Organizers: MaX, Prace, CINECA

Speakers: Giovanni Pizzi, Leonid Kahle, Spyros Zoupanos, Martin Uhrin, Sebastiaan Huber (EPFL, Switzerland).

Topics: The PRACE-MaX tutorial was targeted at students, postdocs and researchers interested in applying high-throughput computations in their research, and in particular to those interested in learning how to use the AiiDA platform.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 27

Involvement: The feedback was overall very positive, with the tutorial graded with an average vote of 9.0 out of 10, and all votes between 8 and 10.

Website:

<https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/709/>; <http://www.aiida.net/report-aiida-tutorial-cineca-may-2018/>

10. Spin-orbit coupling in SIESTA: magnetism and other capabilities

Venue & date: ICN2, Barcelona (ES) – June 20-22, 2018

Organizers: MaX, ICN2

Speakers: Ramón Cuadrado (Theory and Simulation Group, ICN2).

Topics: First principles calculations of any magnetic/nonmagnetic system in which spin-orbit coupling (SOC) is relevant using the SIESTA code. Describe the influence of SOC on the electronic structure of the materials, extracting different properties from the SIESTA output files, and also acquire a basic knowledge of the theoretical models on which the calculations are based.

Aims of the lectures:

- Disseminate the new fully relativistic implementation (spin-orbit coupling) and post-processing tools of SIESTA
- Relate SIESTA's existing magnetic capabilities with SOC (non-collinear)
- Demonstrate technologically relevant examples (topological insulators, materials for hard drive technologies).

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 15

Website:

<http://icn2.cat/en/events/eventdetail/809/spin-orbit-coupling-in-siesta-magnetism-and-other-capabilities>

11. Path Integral Quantum Mechanics: From the Basics to the Latest Developments

Venue & date: CECAM Headquarters, Lausanne (CH) – June 25-29, 2018

Organizers: MARVEL, CECAM, Psi-k, Swiss National Science Foundation.

Speakers: Stuart Althorpe (University of Cambridge), Nandini Ananth (Cornell University), Sara Bonella (EPFL), David Ceperley (University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign), Michele Ceriotti (EPFL), Xinzheng Li (Peking University), Tom Markland (Stanford University), Ondrej Marsalek (Charles University), Jeremy Richardson (ETH Zürich), Mariana Rossi (Fritz Haber Institute), Michele Parrinello (ETH Zürich).

Topics: The topic of this school was the path integral (PI) approach to quantum mechanics and its application to atomistic simulations in fields ranging from physics and chemistry to biology and materials science. PI simulations extended molecular dynamics methods to include quantum effects, such as zero-point energy and tunneling, which are particularly important for correctly describing the behavior of light atoms, such as hydrogen. Path integral methods arise as the best simulation techniques to treat nuclear quantum effects in high dimensional, realistic systems due to the favorable compromise between simulation cost and accuracy of the results. Since the previous school in 2016, progresses on acceleration techniques, higher order integrators, non-adiabatic ring polymer dynamics, ring-polymer instantons, and improvements to path integral approximations to real time observables to name only a few, were proposed. In this school, we started from introductory lectures for non-experienced participants, and went up to more advanced and recent techniques. We had hands-on sessions, mainly based on the i-PI code, where participants were also able to ask the lecturers and experienced users and developers of PI methods about how to apply them in their own research.

Aims of the lectures:

- Introduce basic and advanced concepts in PI methods
- Provide a hands-on introduction to the i-PI code
- Help the students to get started on simulations related to their main research projects that use path integrals and i-PI

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 50

Website: <https://www.cecarn.org/workshop-0-1528.html>

12. MaX Hackathon

Venue & date: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona (ES) – July 16-20, 2018

Organizers: MaX, CNR, University of Udine, EPFL, ICN2, ICTP, BSC, Juelich

Speakers: Luigi Genovese (CEA), Josh Romero (NVIDIA), Jesus Labarta (BSC), Alexandr Fonari (Schroedinger), Fabiano Corsetti (Synopsis), Daniel Simò (Simune), Carlo Cavazzoni (Cineca).

Topics: The Hackathon offered an informal brainstorming environment and practical coding sessions on the MaX flagship codes (Quantum ESPRESSO, Siesta, Fleur, Yambo, AiiDA), including:

- Working groups active in the development of each flagship code, e.g. targeting the development of new features, performance improvements, performance portability to new architectures including GPUs, benchmarking and profiling.
- Advanced training for developers on selected topics (novel parallel paradigms, emerging MPI and OpenMP features/standards, support of GPUs & HW heterogeneity, HDF5 and parallel IO).
- Transversal coding activities (eg parallel IO, support of common electronic structure formats, GPU support).
- Hands-on session on GPU porting coordinated by NVIDIA developers and parallel profiling coordinated by POP CoE.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 45

Involvement: The course received very positive feedback from the participants. For details see attachment D6.4-A4

Website: <http://www.max-centre.eu/max-hackathon/>

In general, the active involvement of participants and their evaluation of the schools were rated extremely positively. Examples of the questionnaires are shown at the end of this report. Other feedbacks were obtained in different form (e.g. video reported event N.7, or standard evaluation form of HPC centers).

For the future, we plan a more systematic and standardized analysis of the feedback.

3.2 Participation of MaX members as lecturers in other schools and dedicated training

The activity of MaX members in training goes far beyond the organization of schools and workshops. Some lectures about codes, HPC, and modeling were offered within training events organized by others (sometimes such training activity can overlap with dissemination, when the events are also directed to peers). We consider this contribution very valuable also in view of its impact on networking.

A list of lectures offered by MaX members is given below:

06/07/2017 - Carlo Cavazzoni (CINECA)

E-CAM Extreme-Scale State-of-the-Art Workshop, University of Barcelona (ES)

Exascale Challenges: The view from Max

Website: <https://www.cecarn.org/workshop-0-1512.html>

24-28/07/2017 - Davide Sangalli (CNR)

Hands-on Yambo code at Elettra Synchrotron Trieste (Italy)

22/09/2017 - Andrea Ferretti (CNR)

2017 MSSC Summer School on the "ab initio modelling of crystalline and defective solids with the CRYSTAL code". London Imperial College (UK)

Ab initio modelling in solid state chemistry in Crystal Developers

Website: <http://www.imperial.ac.uk/mssc2017/programme/>

15/03/2018 - Uliana Alekseeva (FZJ Juelich)

3rd SPPEXA Workshop on Parallel Programming Models, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen(DE)

Experiences Parallelizing Fleur

Website:

<https://doc.itec.rwth-aachen.de/display/VE/3rd+SPPEXA+Workshop+on+Parallel+Programming+Models>

19-23/03/2018 - Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL), Stefano De Gironcoli (SISSA), Paolo Giannozzi (UniUd)

School on Electron-Phonon Physics from First Principles

Introduction to density functional theory (DFT) - PG

Density functional perturbation theory (DFPT) - SdG

Introduction to Quantum-ESPRESSO (QE) - PG

Calculating ground-state and band structures with QE - PG

Calculating phonons with QE - SdG

Maximally-localised Wannier functions - GP

Introduction to Wannier90 - GP

Wannier interpolation of electron bands - GP

Website: <http://indico.ictp.it/event/8301/overview>

26/03/2018 - Spyros Zoupanos (EPFL)

Seminário do Departamento de Física dos Materiais e Mecânica

Managing computational materials science in the high-throughput era: AiiDA and the Materials Cloud

Website:

<http://portal.if.usp.br/ifusp/pt-br/evento/semin%C3%A1rio-do-dfimt-com-o-dr-spyros-zoupanos>

21-25/05/2018 - Stefano Baroni (SISSA)

Quantum ESPRESSO Workshop, Pennsylvania State University, PA (US)

- *Overview of Density-Functional Theory*
- *Density-Functional Perturbation Theory*

Website: <https://www.mri.psu.edu/mri/events/2018-quantum-espresso>

30-31/05/2018 - Pablo Ordejon (ICN2), Stephan Mohr (BSC)

HPC nano workshop, Barcelona (ES)

- *Materials design at the Exascale*
- *The importance of High Performance Computing to accelerate Material Discovery*

Website: <http://hpcnano.icn2.cat/>

1-10/06/2018 - Paolo Giannozzi (UniUd)

Erice School on "Quantum Crystallography", Erice (IT)

Lesson: *Introduction to DFT and the plane-wave pseudopotential method*

Tutorial: *Periodic DFT calculations with Quantum Espresso*

Website: <http://crystalalice.org/2018/>

21/09/2018 - Andrea Ferretti (Cnr Nano, IT).

2018 MSSC Summer School on the "ab initio modelling of crystalline and defective solids with the CRYSTAL code". London Imperial College (UK)

Ab initio modelling in solid state chemistry in Crystal Developers

Website: <http://www.imperial.ac.uk/mssc2018>

3.3 University courses modules

In the MaX's training plan special attention was paid to Master/PhD students and University teachers, who wish to learn the use of frontier computational methods within their domain. In order to do so, several commitments were taken and have been realized.

1. Thanks to a collaboration between the PhD school in "Physics and Nanosciences" of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, and MaX, a PhD course taught by professor Stefano Baroni (SISSA) was held from April to May 2017 at University of Modena and

Reggio Emilia. The course “**Classical and quantum linear response: from lattice dynamics, to optical spectroscopy, and thermal transport simulations**” has been designed for PhD and Master students.

2. MaX (ICTP and SISSA teams) contributed to the joint SISSA/ICTP **Master in High-Performance Computing 2017-2018** (MHPC) with a set of dedicated lectures on:
 - Introduction to Parallel Computing, I. Girotto (ICTP)
 - Fast Fourier Transforms in Parallel and Multiple Dimensions, I. Girotto & R. Gebauer (ICTP)
 - Electronic structure: from blackboard to source code, S. De Gironcoli (SISSA)

Number of students: 12

Website: <http://mhpc.it>

3. MaX - CNR team contributed to the **MSci Course in Physics** of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, IT, by participating in the design and realization of a new course entitled “Laboratory of Computational Quantum Mechanics”, particularly for what concerns the “hands-on” activities that were performed on MaX flagship codes. This initiative was developed by Andrea Ferretti and Daniele Varsano from MaX (CNR Nano), together with Professor Alice Ruini who is in charge of the course for the University. In addition to the planning, Drs Ferretti and Varsano have taken part in seven laboratory sessions; based on this experience, they are currently exploring the possibility of further developments.

Number of students: 15

Website: <http://www.international.unimore.it/singleins.html?id=80>

4. Fabio Affinito (CINECA) contributed to the course “Computational Statistical Mechanics” lectured by Prof. Giovanni B. Bachelet for the curriculum of **Physics Degree, Università di Roma “La Sapienza”**. This contribution consisted of three lectures (3 hours each), with fundamentals of parallel programming and with a hands-on based on the calculation of phonon dispersion of a graphene layer with Quantum ESPRESSO. The hands-on calculations were run on the MARCONI Cineca’s cluster.

Number of students: 15

Website: <http://www.giovannibachelet.it/CSM-17-18/>

5. A 3 ECTS course entitled “**The physics of Solar Cells: from Single Junction Devices to Nanostructured Systems**” was given to PhD students (School in Physics and Nanosciences, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia) in February 2018 by Dr. Ivan Marri (CNR-Nano). The course comprised 10 hours lecture on advanced topics. Results obtained by applying both Quantum ESPRESSO and Yambo codes in the study of Carrier Multiplication dynamics in nanocrystals have been discussed in details.

3.4 Training through research

Another channel of the MaX training is provided directly by hosting researchers in the CoE labs. This kind of activity is a powerful instrument both for industrial researchers and for academic researchers/PhD students. This offer was very successful: overall 46 young researchers from academic and industrial institutions were hosted in our Labs. Training and hand-on tutorials organized in the CoE labs were mainly dedicated to introduce students and young researchers in the functionalities of the MaX flagship codes and in the method/theory implemented therein for applications in the field of tribology, electronic, optical and transport properties of the material, high-throughput computation and high-throughput data analysis. After the period spent in MaX labs, the visitors were able to set up specific calculations and, in some cases, to implement new features in the codes for their scientific needs.

A list of the training activities organized in our CoE labs in months 19-36 is reported below.

Guest: Dr. Hiroyoshi Momida

Affiliation: Osaka University, Osaka, Japan

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 20/01/2017 – 28/02/2018

Purpose of the visit: Training on FLEUR and usage of FLEUR for the investigation of Topological Insulators.

Guest: Marx Eixarch

Affiliation: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Hosting unit: BSC

Period: February 2017 - September 2017

Purpose of the visit: The visitor was doing his Master Thesis at BSC about large scale electronic structure calculations for metallic systems.

Guest: Victor Garcia

Affiliation: Universidad de Oviedo, Spain

Hosting unit: EPFL - THEOS

Period: 06.03.2017 - 08.03.2017

Purpose of the visit: Discussions with AiiDA core developers about the aiida-siesta plugin for SIESTA code

Guest: Emanuelle Bosoni

Affiliation: Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

Hosting unit: EPFL - THEOS

Period: 08.03.2017

Purpose of the visit: Discussions with AiiDA core developers about the aiida-siesta plugin for SIESTA code

Guest: Dongwook Go

Affiliation: Pohang University of Science and Technology, Pohang, South Korea

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 25/03/2017 – 24/04/2017

Purpose of the visit: Training on FLEUR and usage of FLEUR for the calculation of the Orbital Rashba effect.

Guest: Dr. Bertrand Dupé

Affiliation: Johannes Gutenberg University, Mainz, Germany

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 19/06/2017 – 07/08/2017

Purpose of the visit: Usage of FLEUR for the investigation of the Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction in Co/Pt(111).

Guest: Dominik Gresch

Affiliation: ETH Zurich, Switzerland

Hosting unit: EPFL - THEOS

Period: 17.07.2017 - 21.07.2017

Purpose of the visit: Meeting with developers of aiida-core

Guest: Gareth Tribello

Affiliation: Queen's University of Belfast, Ireland

Hosting unit: EPFL - COSMO (Ceriotti)

Period: 01.08.2017 - 09.09.2017

Purpose of the visit: Integration of PLUMED with Quantum ESPRESSO and AiiDA

Guest: Gareth Tribello

Affiliation: Queen's University of Belfast, Ireland

Hosting unit: EPFL - COSMO (Ceriotti)

Period: 23.09.2017 - 24.09.2017

Purpose of the visit: Integration of PLUMED with Quantum ESPRESSO and AiiDA

Guest: Peter Bouss

Affiliation: RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 01/10/2017 – 28/02/2018

Purpose of the visit: Training on FLEUR and usage of FLEUR for the investigation of the Exchange Interaction in different materials.

Guest: Leonidas Mouchliadis

Affiliation: FORTH (Greece)

Hosting unit: CNR

Period: Dec 11-20 2017

Purpose of the visit: Dr Mouchliadis visited CNR to learn how to run real-time simulations with the Yambo code.

Guest: Dr. Javad Ashemi

Affiliation: Toosi University of Technology, Tehran, Iran

Hosting unit: CNR

Period: 01/02/2018 – 08/08/2018

Purpose of the visit: Training in QE code. After training on the QE package, the visitor performed first principle simulations to study oxygen reduction reaction on metal electrodes.

Guest: Sebastian Meyer

Affiliation: Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Kiel, Germany

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 20/02/2018 – 22/02/2018

Purpose of the visit: Training on FLEUR for the investigation of magnetic interactions.

Guest: Alba Gordó

Affiliation: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Hosting unit: BSC

Period: February 2018 - September 2018

Purpose of the visit: The visitor was doing her Master Thesis at BSC. The thesis was about the investigation of point defects in Tungsten using Density Functional Theory.

Guest: Espen Flage-Larsen

Affiliation: SINTEF, Norway

Hosting unit: EPFL - THEOS

Period: 04.06.2018 - 07.06.2018

Purpose of the visit: AiiDA / aiida-vasp plugin: discussions with core developers and plugin developer Rico Hauselmann

Guest: Robert Clay

Affiliation: Sandia National Laboratory, United States of America

Hosting unit: EPFL - THEOS

Period: 05.06.2018

Purpose of the visit: Discussion about the AiiDA workflow engine and the Sandia workflow solution

Guest: Dr. Michal Hermanowicz

Affiliation: Poznan University of Technology, Poland

Hosting unit: BSC

Period: 13/06/2018 – 05/09/2018

Purpose of the visit: HPC-Europa3 visit. The visitor performed investigations on MXenes using the computational resources of BSC and, among other tools, the Siesta code.

Guest: Matteo Ferri

Affiliation: SISSA

Hosting unit: CNR

Period: June 2018

Purpose of the visit: Dr Ferri visited CNR to learn how to set up Hartree Fock self-consistent calculations in Yambo code.

Guest: Ludger Wirtz

Affiliation: Physics and Materials Science Research Unit, University of Luxembourg

Hosting unit: CNR

Period: June 11-13, 2018

Purpose of the visit: Prof. Wirtz visited CNR to discuss of future collaborations involving the use of the Yambo code.

Guest: Sven Reichardt

Affiliation: Physics and Materials Science Research Unit, University of Luxembourg

Hosting unit: CNR

Period: June 11-13, 2018

Purpose of the visit: Dr. Reichardt visited CNR for discussions on the theory of Raman spectroscopy and possible development in the Yambo code for this purpose.

Guest: Dr. Hyung-Jung Kim

Affiliation: Korea Institute for Advanced Study, Seoul, South Korea

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 01/06/2018 – 30/11/2018

Purpose of the visit: Training on FLEUR and usage of FLEUR for the investigation of Topological Insulators.

Guest: Espen Flage-Larsen

Affiliation: SINTEF, Norway

Hosting unit: EPFL - THEOS

Period: 30.06.2018 - 31.07.2018

Purpose of the visit: AiiDA / aiida-vasp plugin: discussions with core developers and plugin developer Rico Hauselmann

Guest: Gabriela Wójtowicz

Affiliation: Jagiellonian University, Krakow, Poland

Hosting unit: Forschungszentrum Jülich

Period: 13/07/2018 – 20/09/2018

Purpose of the visit: Training on FLEUR and usage of FLEUR for the investigation of Topological Insulators.

4 Conclusions

During months 19-36 we further expanded the training activities following the plan outlined in D6.1. Specific events were organized with the aim of training students and users in the usage of the CoE flagship codes, frontiers HPC developments and best practice to exploit HPC applications in materials science. Many of these specific events were also integrated with practical hands-on sessions devoted to familiarize users in the use of materials science codes or to train developers in practical implementations aimed in enhancing code performance and portability in new architectures. The MaX training activity allowed also the realization of events that gathered teachers from different partner nodes (both from universities and HPC centres) and developers of different codes permitting to provide to the students a large perspective on HPC developments and materials science codes. The large participation and involvement show the overall success of the events. During this period, MaX partners continued to contribute to Master, PhD and University courses offering modules on computational material sciences and advanced HPC developments towards the exascale and hosting students, postdoc and users in their labs for specific and dedicated training.

5 Attachments

D6.4-A1 Evaluation form Yambo school (training event n. 2 page 6)

D6.4-A2 Feedback of the Siesta school (training event n. 4 page 8)

D6.4-A3 Evaluation for Aiida tutorial May 2017 (training event n. 5 page 9)

D6.4-A4 Feedback form for MaX Hackathon (training event n. 12 page 14)

D6.4-A1

Advanced computing of excited state properties in solids and nanostructures with Yambo

April 24-28, 2017

Location: CECAM-HQ-EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland

I am:

27 responses

Course Content

How satisfied were you with the logistics?

On a scale of 1-5 (1 being "not at all") how willing would you be to recommend this tutorial to a colleague ?

27 responses

Any general comments, criticisms, or suggestions on how to improve any aspect of the school? 15 responses (following):

-- If we know before the site of wiki, we can follow better steps.

-- Write step-by-step all the input files (also for QE calculations) to better understand criticism on each variable. Similarly a step-by-step reading of the output would be appreciated. However, I'm aware that those requests are more appropriate for an entry level school rather than for an advanced school.

-- The two "general purpose" talks (Marzari's and the one about the future of parallel computing) were nice, but those are talks that one gets often in other places. Here, given the time constraints of the course and the complexity of the theory behind the code it might have been more useful to devote those slots to either more basic introductions to the formalism or another hands-on session.

-- The tutorial prepared for this school were great! Much clearer and easier to follow than the old tutorials on the website:-) My only suggestion is maybe to record all lectures and put them available online.

-- Truly, this was a fantastic School. In terms of the organisation, lecture order and scheduling, the clarity of the objectives, the relation of lecture material to tractable (and understandable) hands on examples and the level of the material presented everything has been almost perfect. There were only two instances where i found it difficult to follow the material, first during the lecture on Feynman diagrams and secondly during the lecture on trends in parallel computing.

-- Blackboard explanations of more difficult concepts would be appreciated.

-- Feynman diagrams were hard to understand if you have never used them.

-- It would be nice to have a series of YAMBO schools while you are improving the code.

-- In general was very good. I would like to refer some details that could be improved in the next school. One of them is that there were some seats that was difficult to have connectivity to electricity to connect the laptop, the other is that in the talk of "Trends in parallel computing", I didn't knew a lot of the words and concepts that were talked, maybe a more soft way to show what are the components are, the problems of the today's supercomputers and the direction that the technology is taking.

-- Overall the school was extremely useful, well taught and organized. Especially the tutorials. Perhaps the only note (probably due to my lacking background on the subject) is that a little more time could have given to the introductory part on the Feynman diagrams and introduction to linear response theory.

-- Dear Organizers, you did a really good job, thank you a lot for your effort !

--Thanks to the school, now I could understand some aspects of Yambo that were not clear to me when I started exploring yambo by myself. To this end, could be nice to upload the cheatsheet that you gave us also on the yambo website. Could be also interesting to have also an advanced school with more elaborate calculations that one can do in Yambo.

-- Theoretical lectures on Hedin's equations were a little too compressed. For someone new to the topic the derivation could have been too brief, missing the physical ideal behind Dyson equations meaning

-- I would like to specially thank you Conor Hogan for positively support and friendly manner.

-- For someone like me lacking a background in many body physics, the lectures were very difficult to follow. I was hoping for something a bit more at the introductory level. Probably the lecture on Feynman diagrams was the hardest, I honestly did not understand anything. The one on BSE by Myrta Gruning was the one I got the most out of: surely one could get lost in the math, but there was always an effort to connect the equations to the physical processes. One suggestion I could give is to cover less material and do it at a slower pace, thus giving students who are exposed to this material for the very first time a better chance

to follow the lectures. The tutorials were great, really well prepared, very useful indeed. All the instructors did a great job!

6.4-A2

Siesta school on efficient DFT calculations using atomic orbitals

May 23-26, 2017

Venue: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona (ES)

EXIT QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS

The goal of the BSC training evaluation is twofold: on the one hand, to capture the impact of the training program. On the other hand, to allow an insight of the attendees' personal progress. It also provides understanding on how to support them in implementing the learned methodologies/tools in their work.

Education and Training at BSC has designed its Exit Questionnaire based on the well-established Kirkpatrick model of evaluation of professional training. The questionnaire is purposefully very concise and focusing solely on the learning outcomes of the courses.

Below are presented the results specifically for the course you convene. 13 people have responded to the exit questionnaire:

1. How would you rate the overall relevance of this course for you and your studies/work?

2. How effectively the materials used in the course help reinforce your understanding of the represented?

3. The learning activities helped me progress with the material

4. Have you been introduced to a technique or a method that you would like to apply in your research/work or study further?

- 1 Not interested to pursue further topics
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 I'm very interested to implement the methods/ tools

5. If you answered positively to question 4, please indicate which ones you are interested in:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lattice dynamics estimation, phonon spectra
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would like to automate the initial setup step (optimization of pseudopotential and or basis sets generation, lattice constant and other relevant properties). In addition, I would like to have a look to hybrid systems, so I could talk advantages of GPU architectures. Finally, I would like to have a deeper and understanding on tranSiesta and probably its linkages with phonon-electron & electron-electron packages.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DFT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am interested in using MD functionalities of SIESTA. I come from classical MD simulations and looking forward to apply DIF in the near future.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optical properties, relaxation techniques, LDA + U methods
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optical constant calculations using SIESTA, relaxing lattices.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualization, tranSIESTA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AIMD, tranSIESTA

6. How would you rate the overall value of this course?

D6.4-A3

Second edition of the MARVEL/Psi-k/MaX tutorial on High-Throughput computations: general methods and applications using Aiiida.

May 29-31, 2017

Venue: EPFL, Lausanne (CH)

Results of the feedback form

The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive. We report below the main results of the feedback form. The next two plots compare the self-assessed level of knowledge of AiiDA of the participants before and after the tutorial. Remarkably, participants with a “poor” level of knowledge, which represented the relative majority

before the tutorial, were no longer present after the tutorial. The vast majority of the self-evaluations after the tutorial was “satisfactory” or better.

Change in the level of skills before and after the AiiDA tutorial

The following series of plots reports on the evaluations that the instructors received from the participants. The distribution of the responses suggests that the instructors were prepared, available, and capable to effectively motivate the participants.

Results of the feedback form on the AiiDA instructors

Finally, 92.8% of the participants declared that they would strongly recommend their colleagues to participate to a similar tutorial on high-throughput computations using AiiDA. Also, 75% of the participants said they would like to participate in advanced AiiDA tutorials on topics like workflow development.

D6.4-A4

2018 MaX Hackathon

July 16-20, 2018

Venue: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona (ES)

After the MaX Hackathon we asked the participants to fill a feedback form. In the following we present the summary results of the questionnaire.

Please rate the training/hands-on sessions

Please rate the coding sessions

Please rate the lectures, and round tables

How do you rate the duration of the hackathon?

24 responses

Free comments from the participants:

“Nice workshop”.

“The dates were fixed with a too-short notice, and many people (some of them being key-developers) were not able to come, as they had already booked their vacations. Notifying more in advance would increase the attendance.”

“Great event, thanks to the organizers”.

“The coders from the different packages tend to be a little insulated, and can leave guests not belonging to any code a bit left out. Could use some activities to encourage mixing!”

“Bad air conditioning and microphones”

“Several rooms close by would be better, that groups can form for discussions, and work better together, otherwise too loud in the main room. Too many talks and hands on sessions, that were not of interest to everybody. Presentations of who works on what not needed, because we had a program and goals written beforehand. But overall thanks a lot for organizing, it was fun! ;-)”

“Air conditioning was not always working”.

“Hackathon was great. Thanks to the organisers”.

“Fully satisfied!”

“Logistics: introduce and advertise the hackathon much earlier. Hackathon organization: focus on teams, discuss and introduce specific tasks on the first day, create inter-team communication mechanisms if/as needed and organize the subsequent work around the pre-defined tasks (not necessarily coding). Report on the advances daily.”

“Having one room for classes/round table and another (or more) for the code sessions would have been better (there was an extra room somewhere). For the coding session the tables could have been then arranged for small groups (3-4). With the present arrangement it was difficult to interact with more than one at the time.”

“Maybe more rooms are needed. 1 room when many people talk/collaborate makes it too noisy when someone needs to coordinate on something.”

“I would have preferred to have at least another room, for discussions in smaller groups (but as close as possible to the main room, to facilitate movements and avoid that one group has to split from the rest: meeting all developers together and cross-code discussions were very effective). For the rest, everything was great!!”

“The Hackathon was very useful for the internal developments of the code, also including the tutorials. One aspect to possibly improve could be the inter-code interaction and the interaction with experts of HPC centers. A different organization of the round-tables could help in reaching such goal.”

“Maybe just one more day for hacking.”

“GPU hands-on session was awesome and it helped a lot to have Josh around afterwards to answer the questions. The profiling (extrae) presentation was interesting, but there was no specialists to assist afterwards, which impeded the progress considerably”.

“More rooms for coding in order to talk to other groups more efficiently with less background noise.”

“Great experience”.

“It would be nice to have more time since the Hackathon was announced to prepare collaborations and to plan the coding sessions”.

On a scale of 1-5 (1 being “not at all”, 5 being “extremely”) how you are satisfied with the Hackathon?

24 responses

